

GESTATION-SPECIFIC REFERENCE INTERVALS FOR THE THYROID-STIMULATING HORMONE (TSH) IN A SAMPLE OF PREGNANT WOMEN ATTENDING PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTERS IN BABYLON PROVINCE

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Abstract: Considering to downward shift of the TSH reference range occurs during pregnancy, with a reduction in both the lower and the upper limit of maternal TSH relative to the typical nonpregnant TSH reference range and the changes in thyroid physiology associated with pregnancy and poor outcomes related to abnormal maternal thyroid function, international guidelines recommend using population-based trimester-specific reference intervals (RIs) for thyroid testing. The aim of this study is establishing a suitable RI of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) in pregnant Iraqi women in order to solve this problem.

Methods: A total of 40 women visiting primary health care centers in Babylon province aged 19 to 35 years (10 non pregnant women, 10 pregnant women in first trimesters: T1 (1-12 weeks), 10 pregnant women in second trimesters: T2 (13-25 weeks), and 10 pregnant women in third trimesters: T3 (26-41 weeks) were used in the study. Women followed in primary health care centers in Babylon province were enrolled in the reference interval study after applying exclusion criteria related to medical and prenatal history.

Results: The upper limits for the TSH reference range in pregnant groups were all lower than that of upper reference limits of non pregnant group. Also the lowest value of the upper limit for TSH and T3 was detected in the second trimester, the lowest value of the lower limit for TSH and T3 was detected in the third trimester.

Conclusions: Establishing gestation- and laboratory-specific RIs, especially for TSH, is essential for diagnosing thyroid disorders in pregnancy. Maternal thyroid function, especially TSH and free T3, changed during the course of pregnancy.

1. INTRODUCTION

The thyroid is an endocrine gland located in the inferior, anterior neck, and it is responsible for the formation and secretion of the thyroid hormones as well as iodine homeostasis within the human body. The thyroid produces approximately 90% inactive thyroid hormone, or thyroxine (T₄), and 10% active thyroid hormone, or triiodothyronine (T₃). Inactive thyroid hormone is converted peripherally to either activated thyroid hormone or an alternative inactive thyroid hormone. [1]

Thyroid disease is the second most common endocrine disorder after diabetes in pregnancy. Thyroid disease poses a substantial challenge on the physiology of pregnant women and has significant maternal and fetal implications. Research shows during pregnancy, the size of the thyroid gland increases by 10% in countries with adequate iodine stores and by approximately 20% to 40% in countries with iodine deficiency. During pregnancy, thyroid hormone production increases by around 50% along with a similar increase in total daily iodine requirements. Thyroid dysfunction in pregnant women including hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism requires close monitoring and treatment as warranted. Occasionally, pregnancy may be complicated by thyroid nodules and thyroid cancer requiring further intervention. [2,3]

Thyroid-stimulating hormone, also known as TSH, Is a glycoprotein hormone produced by the anterior pituitary. It is the primary stimulus for thyroid hormone production by the thyroid gland. It also exerts growth effects on thyroid follicular cells leading to enlargement of the thyroid. The hypothalamic-pituitary axis regulates TSH release. Specifically, neurons in the hypothalamus release TRH, or thyroid-releasing hormone, which stimulates thyrotrophs of the anterior pituitary to secrete TSH.

TSH, in turn, stimulates thyroid follicular cells to release thyroid hormones In the form of T3 or T4. [4,5].

A downward shift of the TSH reference range occurs during pregnancy, with a reduction in both the lower and the upper limit of maternal TSH relative to the typical nonpregnant TSH reference range .

Additionally, utilizing population-based, trimester-specific RIs for thyroid tests that were generated from local populations has been recommended by national guidelines around the world due to racial and geographic variances in population, data representing a provider's laboratory [6]. There has been a considerable amount of data documenting population-based gestational RIs since these guideline statements. Although the studies reveal significant variation in the reference limit values for TSH, mostly these fixed RIs recommended by the American Thyroid Association (ATA) and the American Endocrine Association are still in use: first trimester, 0.1–2.5 mIU/L; second trimester, 0.2–3.0 mIU/L; third trimester, 0.3–3.0 mIU/L [7].

In addition, the 2017 ATA guideline updated the recommendation by suggesting a new threshold of 4 mIU/L for the TSH upper reference limit in early pregnancy [6].

However, recommendation 1 of ATA guideline suggested that When possible, population-based trimester-specific reference ranges for serum TSH should be defined through assessment of local population data representative of a health care provider's practice. To address this issue, we aimed to establish gestational and laboratory-specific RIs for TSH and determine its trend throughout the pregnancy.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 40 women visiting primary health care centers in Babylon province aged 19 to 35 years (10 non pregnant women, 10 pregnant women in first trimesters: T1 (1-12 weeks), 10 pregnant women in second trimesters: T2 (13-25 weeks), and 10 pregnant women in third trimesters: T3 (26-41 weeks) were used in the study.

Additionally, women who had any chronic/autoimmune disease (e.g., hypertension, diabetes, rheumatoid arthritis, psoriasis, and cancer) and pregnancy complications (e.g., gestational diabetes, preeclampsia, gestational hypertension, spontaneous abortion) were further ruled out.

Body mass index (BMI) was a measure by weight in kilograms divided by the square of height in meters. Also blood pressure and Serum levels of TSH and T3 were measured by using the BioTek 800 TS absorbance reader (an affordable, high-quality microplate reader for assays) , CALBIOTECH Thyroid Stimulating Hormone (TSH) ELISA KIT and CALBIOTECH Triiodothyronine (T3) ELISA Kit by taking

about 5 mL of the maternal venous blood using disposable syringes. The serum sample was separated by centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 5 to 10 minutes and stored until analysis.

Statistical analysis

Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23.0 (SPSS, Chicago, USA) was used for statistical analysis of the data. Data was given in the form of arithmetical mean values and standard deviation. The median, lower and upper limits (LL and UL) of the reference intervals were determined

3. RESULTS

As described in the table (1), figure (1) and figure (2) the demographic data concerning women attending primary health care centers in Babylon province the median maternal age of non pregnant group was 24.50 years (range: 18-32 years). Group T1 women in first trimesters the median maternal age was 26.50 years (range: 16-35 years), whereas T2 group women in second trimesters the median maternal age was 25.50 years (range: 18-32 years) and the median maternal age in T3: women in third trimesters was 26.50 years (range: 27-33 years).

The median gestational age of group T1 was 8.50 weeks (range: 4-12 weeks), group T2 was 21.50 weeks (range: 16-24 weeks) and 26.50 weeks (range: 27-33 weeks).

A woman's blood pressure median in non pregnant group was 8/12 mm Hg (range: 7/9-11/13 mm Hg), while group T1 the median blood pressure was 8/11 mm Hg (range: 5/9-10/13 mm Hg), also group T2 median blood pressure was 8/12 mm Hg (range: 5/9-8/14 mm Hg) and median blood pressure of T3 group was 8/12 mm Hg (7/11-8/12 mm Hg).

The median maternal body mass index of non pregnant group was 27.30 kg/m² (range: 22.3-30.10 kg/m²), T1 group median body mass index was

23.75 kg/m² (range: 20.60-31.50 kg/m²), T2 group median body mass index was 25.65 kg/m² (range: 19.50-30.20 kg/m²) and T3 group median body mass index was 27.00 kg/m² (range: 20.70-39.80 kg/m²).

Table (1) Demographic details in a Sample of Pregnant Women Attending Primary Health Care Centers in Babylon Province.

Groups	Maternal age years*	Gestational age, weeks*	LP	HP	BMI
Non pregnant	24.80±4.68		8.2±1.13	11.60±1.07	24.88±2.49
	24.50(18-32)	-	8.00 (7-11)	12.00 (9-13)	27.30 (22.3-30.10)
T1	25.50±5.4	8.60±2.50	7.40±1.42	11.00±1.24	24.96±3.22
	26.50(16-35)	8.50(4-12)	8.00(5-10)	11.00(9-13)	23.75(20.60-31.50)
T2	25.30±5.71	21.30±2.31	7.50±0.97	11.8±1.39	25.24±3.60
	25.50(17-34)	21.50(16-24)	8.00 (5-8)	12.00(9-14)	25.65(19.50-30.20)
T3	25.80±5.65	31.40±1.17	7.90±0.31	11.9±0.31	27.95±4.88
	26.50(27-33)	31.50(30-33)	8.00(7-8)	12.00(11-12)	27.00(20.70-39.80)

Data are presented in first row for each group as mean ± SD and second row Median (lower limit-upper limit). T1: women in first trimesters; T2: women in second trimesters; T3: women in third trimesters; LP: Low pressure ;HP: High pressure ; BMI: Body Mass Index.

Figure (1) comparative of Maternal's age years* and Gestational age, weeks* between groups

T1: women in first trimesters; T2: women in second trimesters; T3: women in third trimesters.

Figure (2) comparative of Maternal's blood pressure (mm Hg) and body mass index (kg/m²)between groups

T1: women in first trimesters; T2: women in second trimesters; T3: women in third trimesters; LP: Low pressure ;HP: High pressure ; BMI: Body Mass Index.

The results of Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone TSH as shown in the table

(2) and figure (3) exposed The TSH reference range in the first, second and third trimesters was 0.42 to 1.94 mIU/L, 0.30 to 1.71 mIU/L,

0.12 to 3.00 mIU/L, respectively (Table 2). The upper limits for the TSH reference range were all significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) lower than that of upper reference limits recommended by ATA (2.5 mIU/L for the first trimester, 3 mIU/L in the second and third trimester). Also The upper limits for the TSH reference range were all lower than that of upper reference limits of non pregnant group (0.40-3.01 mIU/L). Even though the lowest value of the upper limit for TSH was detected in the second trimester, the lowest value of the lower limit for TSH was detected in the third trimester.

Table (2) Trimester-specific reference intervals for Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone TSH (mIU/L) details in a Sample of Pregnant Women Attending Primary Health Care Centers in Babylon Province comparing with American Thyroid Association (ATA) Guidelines .

Trimester	Mean \pm SD	Median	Lower limit	Upper limit	ATA maternal recommendatin*
Non pregnant	1.30 \pm 0.78	1.0580	0.40	3.01	-
T1	0.81 \pm 0.45	0.70	0.42	1.94	0.1 to 2.5
T2	0.67 \pm 0.49	0.50	0.30	1.71	0.2 to 3.0
T3	0.62 \pm 0.84	0.38	0.12	3.00	0.3 to 3.0

T1: women in first trimesters; T2: women in second trimesters; T3: women in third trimesters;

*Guidelines from the 2011 ATA recommendation maternal TSH between 0.1 to 2.5 mIU/L in the first trimester, 0.2 to 3.0 mIU/L in the second trimester, and 0.3 to 3.0 mIU/L in the third trimester

Figure (3) Trimester-specific reference intervals for Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone TSH (mIU/L) comparing with American Thyroid Association (ATA) Guidelines .

T1: women in first trimesters; T2: women in second trimesters; T3: women in third trimesters.

***Guidelines from the 2011 ATA recommendation maternal TSH between 0.1 to 2.5 mIU/L in the first trimester, 0.2 to 3.0 mIU/L in the second trimester, and 0.3 to 3.0 mIU/L in the third trimester**

The results of FreeTriiodothyronine (T3) pg/mL as shown in table (3) and figure (4) the median of free T3 in non pregnant womens was 1.05 pg/mL (range: 0.95-4.07 pg/mL) , The median of T1 group was 3.63 pg/mL (range: 2.85-5.62 pg/mL), The median of T2 group was 3.32 pg/mL (range: 0.99-5.40) and The median of T3 group was 3.23 pg/mL (range: 0.93-10.52 pg/mL).

Even though the lowest value of the upper limit for freeT3 was detected in the second trimester and the lowest value of the lower limit for free T3 was detected in the third trimester. These results are identical to the results of the TSH in the lowest value of the upper limit and the lowest value of the lower limit.

Table (3) Free Triiodothyronine levels details in a Sample of Pregnant Women Attending Primary Health Care Centers in Babylon Province

Trimester	Mean \pm SD	Median	Lower limit	Upper limit
Non pregnant	2.46 \pm 1.13	1.05	0.95	4.07
T1	3.90 \pm 3.07	3.63	2.85	5.62
T2	3.12 \pm 1.18	3.32	0.99	5.40
T3	3.72 \pm 2.70	3.23	0.93	10.52

T1: women in first trimesters; T2: women in second trimesters; T3: women in third trimesters.

Figure (4) Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone (TSH) and Free Triiodothyronine levels in a Sample of Pregnant Women Attending Primary Health Care Centers in Babylon Province.

T1: women in first trimesters; T2: women in second trimesters; T3: women in third trimesters.

4. DISCUSSION

Thyroid-Stimulating Hormone (TSH) has been widely accepted as the universal screening tool for thyroid dysfunction in patients, including pregnant women[8]. The result of TSH level showed there is clearly decrease in first and second and third trimester. decrease in serum TSH is observed during the first trimester because of elevated levels of serum hCG directly stimulating the TSH receptor and thereby increasing thyroid hormone production [6]. The serum TSH in the second and third trimesters remain lower than in nonpregnant women this result agree with [9,10]

The TSH lower limit in the first, second and third trimesters was higher than ATA lower limit but lower than in non pregnant lower limit maybe because of different methods of analysis, although this variation is not clinically significant [11]. One approach to reducing this variability is to use the Multiple of Medians calculation to compare values between assays. This calculation divides an individual value by the population median [12].

The results of maternal body mass index reveals an increase with the progression of pregnancy, and this is a logical and acceptable where Maternal weight gain in pregnancy can offer a good means of assessing the wellbeing of the pregnant mother [13] this result agree with [14].

The assessment of blood pressure is fundamental to the provision of safe obstetrical care [15]. The blood pressure results of this study reveals there was non significant increase in maternal blood pressure when compared with non pregnant women. This result indicates that the decrease in the TSH level does not affect blood pressure. Thyroid hormones and TSH have profound effects on cardiovascular functions, suggesting that TSH may contribute to the development of elevated blood pressure [16].

Thyroid hormones are involved in glucose metabolism and homeostasis through multiple ways and the associations between thyroid dysfunction and glucose abnormality have been well established. However, T3 has long been overlooked, even though T3 plays a significant role in glucose regulation [17]. the results of this study exposed gradually increasing in T3 concentration with increasing gestational age this result agree with [18].

The results of the current study displays that there is a relationship between the decreasing of TSH and the rising of free T3 hormone in the first, second and third trimester of pregnancy this result agree with [19,20].

5. Conclusions:

1. Considering the lack of local data regarding the population- based reference intervals for thyroid function tests in pregnant Iraqi women, using the reference limits recommended by ATA.
2. Maternal thyroid function, especially TSH and free T3, changed during the course of pregnancy.
3. The tendency of hormone levels toward high TSH levels and low free T3 levels in the first trimester and high free T3 levels and low TSH levels in the third trimester.

Recommendations

1. Further studies to develop gestation-specific reference intervals (RI) for the thyroid-stimulating hormone by using large samples of wider areas within the province even the rest of the other governorates in Iraq.
2. Periodic follow-up: TSH levels must be monitored during pregnancy and re-examined regularly, and treatment changed if necessary.

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